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MANDAÇAIA – WHICH I CALL “MANDAÇAIA-DA-CAATINGA” (*Melipona mandacaia*)

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Abstract

Meliponiculture in Brazil is a 100-year-old practice. Breeding requires establishing behaviour, observing the patterns of nature and the biology of the species to be bred in captivity, as well as the appropriate type of nest. Brazil has approximately 260 honey-producing species. I started breeding bees on 16/08/2012, and, at first, there were just colonies of “mandaçaia”, which I describe as Mandaçaia-da-caatinga (*Melipona mandacaia* - Smith, 1863), rescued from a 6-hectare deforest area in the rural area of Juazeiro-BA, in the Salitre region, bathed by the river of the same name. The boxes were small with a capacity of 3.5 litres each. In October of the same year I developed the box I called SANTOS, with a volume of 5880 millilitres, and the first colonies in the new hive date from 15/10/2012. Over the course of a decade, the colonies have multiplied to a total of 756 new colonies. Many of these have been sold to local breeders in the open or dry Caatinga areas where the species occurs, and 166 colonies have been donated to institutions and breeders. There are 140 colonies of the aforementioned bee in the breeding area. In respect to the species, in the first half of the 1960s, through my paternal uncles, when they cut down a *Schinopsis brasiliensis*, brauna tree to extract wood used to cover a rural residence, there was a colony of the bee here. My relatives removed the branch and took it to the residence, which was always treated as a tenement, which served as a source of honey to treat illnesses, particularly respiratory illnesses. Both my paternal and maternal relatives always raised the mandaçaia in the tenements, bees that were taken from the drills (deforestation) to open the pits. I've lived with this bee since early childhood. In fact, my mother always treated her children for any respiratory discomfort with this bee's honey. Therefore, all the knowledge, I would say teachings, about this topic are empirical and not scientific. But the challenges are many: in 2018/19, the kleptoparasite *Nausibius clavicornius* was introduced into the brood through 15 colonies of the jandaíra (*Melipona subnitida*) from the states of Paraíba and Rio Grande do Norte, which led to the destruction of 51 “mandaçaia” colonies. It's worth emphasising that it was difficult to eliminate the parasite from the infested colonies, and what has been understood about the sustainability of bees in captivity is complicated, as there is always the possibility of partial or even total loss of the herd. It's worth saying that it's only conservation if it's within the area of occurrence, or preservation only in the natural environment. So, I've always been familiar with so-called rational breeding, albeit in the most primitive moulds, such as the tenements hanging from the porches of rural houses.

